

Neutrosophic Weakly Generalized open and Closed Sets

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Abstract: Smarandache presented and built up the new idea of Neutrosophic concepts from the Neutrosophic sets. A.A. Salama presented Neutrosophic topological spaces by utilizing the Neutrosophic sets. Point of this paper is we present and concentrate the ideas Neutrosophic Weakly Generalized Closed Set in Neutrosophic topological spaces and its Properties are talked about subtleties

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1. Introduction

Smarandache's neutrosophic framework have wide scope of constant applications for the fields of Electrical & Electronic, Artificial Intelligence, Mechanics, Computer Science ,Information Systems, Applied Mathematics , basic leadership. Prescription and Management Science and so forth. In 1965 ,Zadeh proposed Fuzzy set(FS), and Atanassov [1] proposed intuitionistic Fuzzy set (IFS) in 1983 .Topology is an old style subject, as a speculation topological spaces many sort of topological spaces presented over the year. Smarandache [5] characterized the Neutrosophic set on three segment Neutrosophic sets(T Truth, I-Indeterminacy, F-Falsehood). Neutrosophic topological spaces(NS-T-S) presented by Salama [10] et al., R.Dhavaseelan [3], SaiedJafari are introduced Neutrosophic generalized closed sets Point of this paper is we present and concentrate the ideas Neutrosophic Weakly Generalized Closed Set in Neutrosophic topological spaces and its Properties are talked about subtleties

2. Preliminaries

In this part, we review required essential definition and results of Neutrosophic sets

Definition 2.1 [5] Let N_X^* be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic set R_1^* is a object having the form

$$R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \},$$

$\mu_{R_1^*}(r)$ -represents the degree of membership function

$\sigma_{R_1^*}(r)$ -represents degree indeterminacy function and then

$\gamma_{R_1^*}(r)$ -represents the degree of non-membership function

Definition 2.2 [5] Neutrosophic set $R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$, on N_X^* and $\forall r \in N_X^*$ then complement of R_1^* is $R_1^{*C} = \{ \langle r, \gamma_{R_1^*}(r), 1 - \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \mu_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$

Definition 2.3 [5] Let R_1^* and R_2^* are two Neutrosophic sets, $\forall r \in N_X^*$

$$R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}, R_2^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_2^*}(r), \sigma_{R_2^*}(r), \gamma_{R_2^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$$

Then $R_1^* \subseteq R_2^* \Leftrightarrow \mu_{R_1^*}(r) \leq \mu_{R_2^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r) \leq \sigma_{R_2^*}(r) \& \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \geq \gamma_{R_2^*}(r)$

Definition 2.4 [5] Let N_X^* be a non-empty set, and Let R_1^* and R_2^* be two Neutrosophic sets are

$$R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}, R_2^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_2^*}(r), \sigma_{R_2^*}(r), \gamma_{R_2^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$$
 Then

1. $R_1^* \cap R_2^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r) \cap \mu_{R_2^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r) \cap \sigma_{R_2^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \cup \gamma_{R_2^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$
2. $R_1^* \cup R_2^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r) \cup \mu_{R_2^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r) \cup \sigma_{R_2^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \cap \gamma_{R_2^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$

Definition 2.5 [11] Let N_X^* be non-empty set and NS_τ be the collection of Neutrosophic subsets of N_X^* satisfying, the accompanying properties:

1. $0_N, 1_N \in NS_\tau$
2. $N_{T_1} \cap N_{T_2} \in NS_\tau$ for any $N_{T_1}, N_{T_2} \in NS_\tau$
3. $\cup N_{T_i} \in NS_\tau$ for every $\{N_{T_i} : i \in j\} \subseteq NS_\tau$

Then the space (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is called a Neutrosophic topological spaces (NS-T-S).

The component of NS_τ are called NS-OS (Neutrosophic open set)

and its complement is NS-CS (Neutrosophic closed set)

Example 2.6. Let $N_X^* = \{r\}$ and $\forall r \in N_X^*$

$$R_1^* = \langle r, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \rangle, R_2^* = \langle r, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{8}{10} \rangle$$

$$R_3^* = \langle r, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \rangle, R_4^* = \langle r, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{8}{10} \rangle$$

Then the collection $NS_\tau = \{0_N, R_1^*, R_2^*, R_3^*, R_4^*, 1_N\}$ is called a NS-T-S on X.

Definition 2.7 Let (N_X^*, NS_τ) , be a NS-T-S and $R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$ be a

Neutrosophic set in N_X^* . Then R_1^* is said to be

1. Neutrosophic α -closed set [2] (NS- α CS in short) $NS-cl(NS-in(NS-cl(R_1^*))) \subseteq R_1^*$,
2. Neutrosophic pre-closed set [14] (NS-PCS in short) $NS-cl(NS-in(R_1^*)) \subseteq R_1^*$,
3. Neutrosophic regular closed set [5] (NS-RCS in short) $NS-cl(NS-in(R_1^*)) = R_1^*$,
4. Neutrosophic semi closed set [7] (NS-SCS in short) $NS-in(NS-cl(R_1^*)) \subseteq R_1^*$,
5. Neutrosophic generalized closed set [3] (NS-GCS in short) $NS-cl(R_1^* \subseteq H$ whenever $R_1^* \subseteq H$ and H is a NS-OS,
6. Neutrosophic generalized pre closed set [9] (NS-GPCS in short) $NS-pcl(R_1^*) \subseteq H$ whenever $R_1^* \subseteq H$ and H is a NS-OS,

7. Neutrosophic α generalized closed set [8] (NS- α GCS in short) $NS-\alpha-cl(R_1^*) \subseteq H$ whenever $R_1^* \subseteq H$ And H is aNS-OS,
8. Neutrosophic generalized semi closed set [13](NS-GSCS in short) $NS-Scl(R_1^*) \subseteq H$ whenever $R_1^* \subseteq H$ and H is aNS-OS.

Definition 2.8. (N_X^*, NS_τ) , be a NS-T-S and $R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(r), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$. Then

Neutrosophic closure of R_1^* is

$$NS-Cl(R_1^*) = \cap \{ H : H \text{ is a NS-CS in } N_X^* \text{ and } R_1^* \subseteq H \}$$

Neutrosophic interior of R_1^* is

$$NS-Int(R_1^*) = \cup \{ M : M \text{ is a NS-OS in } N_X^* \text{ and } M \subseteq R_1^* \}.$$

Definition 2.9. Let (N_X^*, NS_τ) , be a NS-T-S and $R_1^* = \{ \langle r, \mu_{R_1^*}(r), \sigma_{R_1^*}(x), \gamma_{R_1^*}(r) \rangle : r \in N_X^* \}$

$NS-Sint(R_1^*) = \cup \{ G : G \text{ is a NS-SOS in } N_X^* \text{ and } G \subseteq R_1^* \}$,

$NS-Scl(R_1^*) = \cap \{ K : K \text{ is a NS-SCS in } N_X^* \text{ and } R_1^* \subseteq K \}$.

$NS-\alpha int(R_1^*) = \cup \{ G : G \text{ is a NS-}\alpha OS \text{ in } N_X^* \text{ and } G \subseteq R_1^* \}$,

$NS-\alpha cl(R_1^*) = \cap \{ K : K \text{ is a NS-}\alpha CS \text{ in } N_X^* \text{ and } R_1^* \subseteq K \}$.

3. Neutrosophic Weakly Generalized Closed Set

In this section we introduce Neutrosophic weakly generalized closed set and have studied some of its properties.

Definition 3.1 An (NS)S R_1^* in an (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is said to be a Neutrosophic weakly generalized closed set ((NS-WG)CS) $NS-cl(NS-in(R_1^*)) \subseteq U$ whenever $R_1^* \subseteq U$, U is (NS)OS in N_X^* .

The family of all (NS-WG)CSs of an (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is denoted by (NS-WG)CS(N_X^*).

Example 3.2: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a (NS)T on N_X^*

Where $N_T = \langle r, (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}), (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}) \rangle$.

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}) \rangle$ is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Theorem 3.3: Every (NS)CS is a (NS-WG)CS but not conversely.

Proof: Let R_1^* be a (NS)CS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) ,. Let U be a Neutrosophic open set such that $R_1^* \subseteq U$. Since R_1^* is Neutrosophic closed, $NS-cl(R_1^*) = R_1^*$ and hence $NS-cl(R_1^*) \subseteq U$. But $NS-cl(NS-in(R_1^*)) \subseteq NS-cl(A) \subseteq U$. Therefore $NS-cl(NS-in(R_1^*)) \subseteq U$. Hence R_1^* is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Example 3.4: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a (NS) N_T on N_X^* ,

where $N_T = \langle r, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}) \rangle$.

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}) \rangle$ is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^*

but not an (NS)CS in N_X^* since $NS-cl(R_1^*) = T^c \neq R_1^*$

Theorem 3.5: Every (NS) CS is a (NS-WG)CS but not conversely.

Proof: Let R_1^* be a (NS) CS in N_X^* and let $R_1^* \subseteq U$ and U is a (NS)OS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) ,. By hypothesis, $NS-cl(NS-in(NS-cl(R_1^*))) \subseteq R_1^*$. Therefore $NS-cl(NS-in((R_1^*))) \subseteq NS-cl(NS-in(NS-cl(R_1^*))) \subseteq R_1^* \subseteq U$. Therefore $NS-cl(NS-in((R_1^*))) \subseteq U$. Hence R_1^* is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Example 3.6: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)Ton N_X^* where

$$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS) CS in N_X^*

since $R_1^* \subseteq N_T$ but $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*))) = \langle r, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right) \rangle \not\subseteq R_1^*$.

Theorem 3.7: Every (NS)GCS is a(NS-WG)CS but not conversely.

Proof: Let R_1^* be a(NS)GCS in N_X^* and let $R_1^* \subseteq U$ and U is a(NS)OS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) . Since $NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*) \subseteq U$, $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*)$. That is $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*) \subseteq U$. Therefore $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq U$. Hence R_1^* is a(NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Example 3.8: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS) N_T on N_X^*

where $N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle .$

Then (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}\right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS)GCS in N_X^*

since $R_1^* \subseteq N_T$ but $NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*) = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle \not\subseteq N_T$.

Theorem 3.9: Every (NS)RCS is a(NS-WG)CS but not conversely.

Proof: Let R_1^* be a(NS)RCS in N_X^* and let $R_1^* \subseteq U$ and U is a(NS)OS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) . Since R_1^* is (NS)RCS, $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) = R_1^* \subseteq U$. This implies $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq U$. Hence R_1^* is a(NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Example 3.10:

Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS) Ton N_X^* , where

$$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

The (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS)RCS in N_X^* since $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \neq 0\sim R_1^*$.

Theorem 3.11: Every (NS)PCS is a(NS-WG)CS but not conversely.

Proof: Let R_1^* be a(NS)PCS in N_X^* and let $R_1^* \subseteq U$ and U is a(NS)OS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) . By Definition, $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq R_1^*$ and $R_1^* \subseteq U$. Therefore $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq U$. Hence R_1^* is a(NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Example 3.12:

Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* ,

$$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{0}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS)PCS in N_X^*

since $\text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(R_1^*)) = T^c \notin R_1^*$.

Theorem 3.13: Every (NS) GCS is a(NS-WG)CS .

Proof: Let R_1^* be a(NS) GCS in N_X^* and let $R_1^* \subseteq U$ and U is a (NS)OS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) , By Definition, $R_1^* \subseteq \text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(\text{NS-cl}(R_1^*))) \subseteq U$. This implies $\text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(\text{NS-cl}(R_1^*))) \subseteq U$ and $\text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq \text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(\text{NS-cl}(R_1^*))) \subseteq U$. Therefore $\text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(R_1^*)) \subseteq U$. Hence R_1^* is a(NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

Example 3.14:

Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* ,

where $N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle$.

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS) GCS in N_X^* since $\text{NS-}\alpha\text{cl}(R_1^*) = 1\sim \notin N_T$.

Proposition 3.15: (NS)SCS and (NS-WG)CS are independent to each other which can be seen from the following example.

Example 3.16: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^*

$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle$.

Then (NS)S $R_1^* = N_T$ is a(NS)SCS

but not an (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* since $R_1^* \subseteq N_T$

but $\text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(R_1^*)) = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right) \rangle \not\subseteq N_T$.

Example 3.17:

Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* ,

$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{0}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle$.

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS)SCS in N_X^* since $\text{NS-in}(\text{NS-cl}(R_1^*)) = 1\sim \notin R_1^*$.

Proposition 3.18: (NS)GSCS and (NS-WG)CS are independent to each other.

Example 3.19: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* ,

where $N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle$.

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = N_T$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS)GPCS in N_X^* since $R_1^* \subseteq N_T$

but $\text{NS-cl}(\text{NS-in}(R_1^*)) = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle \not\subseteq R_1^*$.

Example 3.20: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_\tau, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* , where

$$N_\tau = \langle r, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right), \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{0}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)CS

but not an (NS)GSCS in N_X^* since $NS\text{-}scl(R_1^*) = 1\sim \notin N_\tau$.

Remark 3.21:

The union of any two (NS-WG)CSs need not be a(NS-WG)CS in general as seen from the following example.

Example 3.22:

Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ be a(NS)TS and

$$\text{let } N_\tau = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_\tau, 1\sim\}$ is a(NS)T on N_X^* and the (NS)Ss

$$R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{0}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{8}{10}\right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle ,$$

$$R_2^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right) \rangle$$

are (NS-WG)CSs but $R_1^* \cup R_2^*$ is not an (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

The following implications are true:

Fig.1

4. NEUTROSOPHIC WEAKLY GENERALIZED OPEN SET

In this section we introduce Neutrosophic weakly generalized open set and have studied some of its properties.

Definition 4.1: An (NS)S R_1^* is said to be a Neutrosophic weakly generalized open set ((NS-WG)OS in short) in (N_X^*, NS_τ) , (NS) the complement $(R_1^*)^C$ is a(NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

The family of all (NS-WG)OS of an (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is denoted by (NS-WG)O(N_X^*).

Example 4.2: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_\tau, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* ,

where $N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle$.

Then the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle$ is a(NS-WG)OS in N_X^* .

Theorem 4.3: For any (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , we have the following:

- (i) Every (NS)OS is a(NS-WG)OS.
- (ii) Every (NS)SOS is a(NS-WG)OS.
- (iii) Every (NS) α OS is a(NS-WG)OS.
- (iv) Every (NS)GOS is a(NS-WG)OS. But the converses are not true in general.

Proof: Straight forward.

The converse of the above statement need not be true in general which can be seen from the following examples.

Example 4.4: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

$$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ is a(NS)T on N_X^* . The (NS)S

$$R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{0}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle$$
 is a(NS-WG)OS in (N_X^*, NS_τ) ,

but not an (NS)OS in N_X^* .

$$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{0}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{8}{10}\right), \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

$$\text{Then the (NS)SR}_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$
 is a(NS-WG)OS

but not an (NS)SOS in N_X^* .

Example 4.6: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ be a(NS)T on N_X^* , where $N_T = \langle r, (0.5, 0.7), (0.5, 0.3) \rangle$.

$$\text{Then the (NS)S } R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle$$
 is a(NS-WG)OS

but not an (NS) α OS in N_X^* .

Example 4.7: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

$$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ is a(NS)T on N_X^* .

$$\text{The (NS)S } R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle$$
 is a(NS-WG)OS

but not an (NS)POS in N_X^* .

Remark 4.8:

The intersection of any two (NS-WG)OSs need not be a(NS-WG)OS in general.

Example 4.9: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ be a(NS)TS and

$$\text{let } N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle .$$

Then $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$ is a(NS)T on N_X^* .

The (NS)Ss $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{0}{10}\right), \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}\right) \rangle$ and

$R_2^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle$ are (NS-WG)OS's but $R_1^* \cap R_2^*$ is not an (NS-WG)OS in N_X^* .

Theorem 4.10:

An (NS)S R_1^* of an (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is a (NS-WG)OS (NS) and only (NS) $F \subseteq NS\text{-in}(NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*))$ whenever F is a (NS)CS and $F \subseteq R_1^*$.

Proof:

Necessity:

Suppose R_1^* is a (NS-WG)OS in N_X^* . Let F be a (NS)CS and $F \subseteq R_1^*$. Then F^c is a (NS)OS in N_X^* such that $(R_1^*)^c \subseteq F^c$. Since $(R_1^*)^c$ is a (NS-WG)CS, $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}((R_1^*)^c)) \subseteq F^c$. Hence $(NS\text{-in}(NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*)))^c \subseteq F^c$. This implies $F \subseteq NS\text{-in}(NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*))$.

Sufficiency:

Let R_1^* be a (NS)S of N_X^* and let $F \subseteq NS\text{-in}(NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*))$ whenever F is a (NS)CS and $F \subseteq R_1^*$. Then $(R_1^*)^c \subseteq F^c$ and F^c is a (NS)OS. By hypothesis, $(NS\text{-in}(NS\text{-cl}(R_1^*)))^c \subseteq F^c$. Hence $NS\text{-cl}(NS\text{-in}((R_1^*)^c)) \subseteq F^c$.

Hence R_1^* is a (NS-WG)OS of N_X^* .

5. APPLICATIONS

In this section, we introduce Neutrosophic $wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space and $wgqT$ space, which utilize Neutrosophic weakly generalized closed set and its characterizations are proved.

Definition 5.1:

An (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is called an Neutrosophic $wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ ((NS) $wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in short) space (NS) every (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* is a (NS)CS in N_X^* .

Definition 5.2:

An (NS)TS (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is called an Neutrosophic $wgqT$ ((NS-WG)qT in short) space (NS) every (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* is a (NS)PCS in N_X^* .

Theorem 5.3: Every (NS) $wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space is a (NS-WG)qT space. But reversal isn't true in general.

Proof: Let N_X^* be a (NS) $wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space and let R_1^* be a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* . By hypothesis R_1^* is a (NS)CS in N_X^* . Since every (NS)CS is a (NS)PCS, R_1^* is a (NS)PCS in N_X^* . Hence N_X^* is a (NS) $wgqT$ space. But reversal isn't true in general.

Example 5.4: Let $N_X^* = \{r_1^*, r_2^*\}$ and

let $NS_\tau = \{0\sim, N_T, 1\sim\}$

$N_T = \langle r, \left(\frac{9}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right), \left(\frac{9}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}\right) \rangle$. Then (N_X^*, NS_τ) , is a (NS-WG)qT space.

But it is not an (NS) $wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space

since the (NS)S $R_1^* = \langle r, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{8}{10}\right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}\right) \rangle$ is (NS-WG)CS but not (NS)CS in N_X^* .

Theorem 5.5: Let (N_X^*, NS_τ) be a (NS)TS and N_X^* is a $(NS)wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space then

- (i) Any union of (NS-WG)CS is a (NS-WG)CS.
- (ii) Any intersection of (NS-WG)OS is a (NS-WG)OS.

Proof:

(i): Let $\{A_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a collection of (NS-WG)CS in an $(NS)wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space (N_X^*, NS_τ) . Therefore every (NS-WG)CS is a (NS)CS. But the union of (NS)CS is a (NS)CS. Hence the Union of (NS-WG)CS is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* .

(ii): It tends to be demonstrated by taking complement at (i).

Theorem 5.6:

An (NS)TS N_X^* is a (NS-WG)qT space (NS) and only (NS) (NS-WG)OS(N_X^*) = (NS)POS(N_X^*).

Proof:

Necessity:

Let R_1^* be a (NS-WG)OS in N_X^* . Then $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* . By hypothesis $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS)PCS in N_X^* . Therefore R_1^* is a (NS)POS in N_X^* . Hence (NS-WG)OS(N_X^*) = (NS)POS(N_X^*).

Sufficiency:

Let R_1^* be a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* . Then $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS-WG)OS in N_X^* . By hypothesis $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS)POS in N_X^* . Therefore R_1^* is a (NS)PCS in N_X^* . Hence N_X^* is a (NS-WG)qT space.

Theorem 5.7: An (NS)TS N_X^* is a $(NS)wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space (NS) and only (NS) (NS-WG)OS (N_X^*) = (NS)OS(N_X^*).

Proof: Necessity:

Let R_1^* be a (NS-WG)OS in N_X^* . Then $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* . By hypothesis $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS)CS in N_X^* . Therefore R_1^* is a (NS)OS in N_X^* . Hence (NS-WG)OS(N_X^*) = (NS)OS(N_X^*).

Sufficiency:

Let R_1^* be a (NS-WG)CS in N_X^* . Then $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS-WG)OS in N_X^* . By hypothesis $(R_1^*)^C$ is a (NS)OS in N_X^* . Therefore R_1^* is a (NS)CS in N_X^* . Hence N_X^* is a $(NS)wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented another class of Neutrosophic closed set to be specific (NS)WG closed set and have examined the connection between Neutrosophic weakly generalized closed set and other existing Neutrosophic closed sets. Likewise we have explored a portion of the properties of Neutrosophic weakly generalized closed set. As an utilization of Neutrosophic weakly generalized closed set we have presented two new spaces specifically $(NS)wT^{\frac{1}{2}}$ space and Neutrosophicwg qT ((NS-WG)qT in short) space and concentrated a portion of their properties.

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